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ECONOMY

Supporting industries help solve the 'middle-income trap' problem.

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(DTTC) - Behind the impressive achievements in exports and attracting foreign investment, a big question remains: How much value has Vietnam actually retained from the process of international economic integration?

It's a story about the economy's position in the global value chain, its ability to master technology, the inherent strength of its businesses, and ultimately, its ability to overcome the middle-income trap and rise to become a developed nation.

The retained value is not commensurate.

Vietnam has become one of the world's major electronics manufacturing hubs, attracting leading technology corporations such as Samsung, LG, and Intel. However, the industries with the largest export value are also the most dependent on imported components, materials, and technology. According to data from the Customs Department in 2025, the electronics, computer, and components industry achieved an export value of US\$107.7 billion, but simultaneously had to import inputs worth US\$150.7 billion.

This reflects a heavy reliance on components, materials, and technology from abroad. Meanwhile, the telephone and components, textile, and footwear industries have significantly higher export values than input imports; the telephone and components industry alone achieved an export-import difference of up to \$42.5 billion.

but mainly in low value-added stages. While high value-creating activities such as technology, design, and branding remain outside the control of domestic businesses, the value retained from exports is limited.

Therefore, developing supporting industries is key to increasing the localization rate and upgrading our position in the global value chain. This is also a typical manifestation of the middle-income trap during the industrialization phase.

An economy can grow rapidly by attracting FDI and expanding exports, but if it fails to increase the domestic value-added ratio and technological capacity, it will be difficult to achieve a leap in productivity and income. In that case, the economy may be deeply integrated but remain stuck in the low-value stages of the global production chain.

Struggling with supporting industries

Over the past decade, Vietnam has not lacked policies to develop supporting industries. From Decree 111/2015/ND-CP to Decree 205/2025/ND-CP, along with numerous programs supporting technological innovation and connecting FDI enterprises with domestic businesses, a basic policy framework has been established.

However, the results achieved have not yet lived up to expectations. Many Vietnamese businesses can produce simple components or parts, but struggle to meet the stringent standards of the global supply chain. From product accuracy and traceability to quality management and on-time delivery, all are significant obstacles.

Meanwhile, multinational corporations are increasingly demanding higher technical standards, data management, and technological innovation capabilities. A notable fact is that many FDI businesses are seeking to increase their sourcing from Vietnam to reduce logistics costs and enhance supply chain flexibility. However, the number of domestic businesses that can meet these requirements remains quite limited.

Looking deeper, supporting industries reflect the transformative capacity of the economy. In this context, the gap between market demand and the capacity of domestic businesses is the biggest bottleneck for supporting industries today.

Attracting FDI, expanding exports, or international integration only creates opportunities; the decisive factor is the ability to transform those opportunities into technology, production capacity, and added value domestically. This is what differentiates an economy that participates in global value chains from one that truly upgrades its position within those chains.

From that perspective, supporting industries serve as a bridge between international integration and endogenous development. When Vietnamese businesses participate more deeply in the supply chains of multinational corporations, they will have easier access to technology, management methods, quality standards, and market experience. It is this learning and accumulation process that creates the real upgrading of the economy.

However, a major limitation currently is that policies for developing supporting industries still mainly focus on individual businesses or sectors, while global value chains operate according to the logic of an ecosystem.

Therefore, the requirement is not only to develop more supporting industrial enterprises, but more importantly, to form complete supporting industrial ecosystems.

In fact, in fields such as electronics, semiconductors, precision mechanics, automobiles, and textiles, it is necessary to form a business ecosystem from leading enterprises to multi-tiered suppliers. In this ecosystem, the State plays the role of creating institutions and infrastructure; FDI enterprises support the development of domestic suppliers; and universities and research institutes provide technology and high-quality human resources.

Effective collaboration among these entities will lay the foundation for a supportive industrial ecosystem with widespread impact across the economy.

Opportunities to participate in the global supply chain.

The restructuring of global supply chains is opening up opportunities for Vietnam to shift from a manufacturing participant to a value creator. Continuing to rely on processing and assembly will make breakthrough growth difficult.

Conversely, developing supporting industries will help Vietnamese businesses participate more deeply in high value-added stages, enhance technological capabilities,

Essentially, this is a question about Vietnam's development path in the 21st century. Will Vietnam continue to occupy low-value links or rise to master technology, brands, and the highest-value-added stages in the global production chain?

The history of East Asian economies shows that overcoming the middle-income trap doesn't begin with producing more, but with creating more value. And supporting industries are one of the crucial foundations for realizing that transformation.

Therefore, supporting industries should be viewed as a strategy to enhance national transformation capacity. The success of supporting industries will determine the ability to transform integration advantages into endogenous strength, thereby creating a foundation for sustainable growth and enhancing Vietnam's position in the global value chain.

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Dr. Huynh Thanh Dien

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